

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Reliability Assessment of Reconfigurable k -out-of- n Systems with Functional Dependency

Appendix A

This appendix first provides a detailed derivation process for the state transition probability parameters $p_{1,1}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ and $p_{1,0}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ of components after a certain period, given the PDF or CDF of the component lifetime distribution. It then presents the analytical expressions for these two parameters when the component lifetime follows an exponential distribution and a Weibull distribution.

(1) Detailed derivation of parameters $p_{1,1}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ and $p_{1,0}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ for $t_2 > t_1 > 0$

Parameter $p_{1,1}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ denotes the probability that component Com remains functioning at time instant t_2 given that it was in a functioning state at time instant t_1 . According to the definition of conditional probability, parameter $p_{1,1}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ can be expanded as:

$$p_{1,1}^{Com}(t_1, t_2) = \Pr\{Com(t_2) = 1 | Com(t_1) = 1\} = \frac{\Pr\{Com(t_2) = 1, Com(t_1) = 1\}}{\Pr\{Com(t_1) = 1\}}. \quad (A.1)$$

Due to the non-repairability of components within the system, the joint probability that a component is in a functioning state at both time instants t_1 and t_2 is equal to the probability that the component is in a functioning state at time instant t_2 , namely $\Pr\{Com(t_2) = 1, Com(t_1) = 1\}$. Assuming PDF and CDF of the lifetime of component Com are $f_{Com}(x)$ and $F_{Com}(x)$, respectively, Eq (A.1) can be further derived as follows:

$$p_{1,1}^{Com}(t_1, t_2) = \frac{\Pr\{Com(t_2) = 1\}}{\Pr\{Com(t_1) = 1\}} = \frac{1 - \int_0^{t_2} f_{Com}(x) dx}{1 - \int_0^{t_1} f_{Com}(x) dx} = \frac{1 - (F_{Com}(t_2) - F_{Com}(0))}{1 - (F_{Com}(t_1) - F_{Com}(0))}. \quad (A.2)$$

Conversely, parameter $p_{1,0}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ denotes the transition probability of component Com from a functioning state at time instant t_1 to a failed state at time instant t_2 . Therefore, the joint probability that a component is in a functioning state at time instant t_1 and in a failed state at time instant t_2 is equal to the probability that the component fails during the time interval $(t_1, t_2]$. Under this circumstance, parameter $p_{1,0}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{1,0}^{Com}(t_1, t_2) &= \Pr\{Com(t_2) = 0 | Com(t_1) = 1\} = \frac{\Pr\{Com(t_2) = 0, Com(t_1) = 1\}}{\Pr\{Com(t_1) = 1\}} \\ &= \frac{\int_{t_1}^{t_2} f_{Com}(x) dx}{1 - \int_0^{t_1} f_{Com}(x) dx} = \frac{F_{Com}(t_2) - F_{Com}(t_1)}{1 - (F_{Com}(t_1) - F_{Com}(0))}. \end{aligned} \quad (A.3)$$

Additionally, the sum of parameters $p_{1,1}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ and $p_{1,0}^{Com}(t_1, t_2)$ is always 1. Therefore, once one of the two parameters is determined, the value of the other parameter can be solved by subtracting the known parameter from 1.

(2) Special cases on parameters $p_{1,1}^{Com}(t, t+1)$ and $p_{1,0}^{Com}(t, t+1)$ under two types of distributions

Let $t_2 = t_1 + 1$ and substitute into (A.2) and (A.3), the state transition parameters of the components within a time unit, namely the CPT parameters needed to be determined for the component nodes in this article, can be calculated. Two cases of component lifetime distribution, including exponential distribution and Weibull distribution, will be shown next.

Regarding an exponential distribution with rate parameter λ , its CDF can be formulated as $F_{Com}(x) = 1 - e^{-\lambda x}$. Therefore, parameters $p_{1,1}^{Com}(t, t+1)$ and $p_{1,0}^{Com}(t, t+1)$ can, respectively, be further deduced as:

$$p_{1,1}^{Com}(t, t+1) = \frac{1 - (F_{Com}(t+1) - F_{Com}(0))}{1 - (F_{Com}(t) - F_{Com}(0))} = \frac{1 - ((1 - e^{-\lambda(t+1)}) - (1 - e^0))}{1 - ((1 - e^{-\lambda t}) - (1 - e^0))} = \frac{e^{-\lambda(t+1)}}{e^{-\lambda t}} = e^{-\lambda}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$p_{1,0}^{Com}(t, t+1) = \frac{F_{Com}(t+1) - F_{Com}(t)}{1 - (F_{Com}(t) - F_{Com}(0))} = \frac{(1 - e^{-\lambda(t+1)}) - (1 - e^{-\lambda t})}{1 - ((1 - e^{-\lambda t}) - (1 - e^0))} = \frac{e^{-\lambda t} - e^{-\lambda(t+1)}}{e^{-\lambda t}} = 1 - e^{-\lambda}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Regarding a Weibull distribution with scale parameter $a > 0$ and shape parameter $b > 0$, its CDF can be formulated as $F_{Com}(x) = \int_0^x ba^{-b}y^{b-1}e^{-\left(\frac{y}{a}\right)^b} dy = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^b}$. Therefore, parameters $p_{1,1}^{Com}(t, t+1)$ and $p_{1,0}^{Com}(t, t+1)$ can, respectively, be further deduced as:

$$p_{1,1}^{Com}(t, t+1) = \frac{1 - (F_{Com}(t+1) - F_{Com}(0))}{1 - (F_{Com}(t) - F_{Com}(0))} = \frac{1 - ((1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t+1}{a}\right)^b}) - (1 - e^0))}{1 - ((1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{a}\right)^b}) - (1 - e^0))} = \frac{e^{-\left(\frac{t+1}{a}\right)^b}}{e^{-\left(\frac{t}{a}\right)^b}} = e^{\frac{t^b - (t+1)^b}{a^b}}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$p_{1,0}^{Com}(t, t+1) = \frac{F_{Com}(t+1) - F_{Com}(t)}{1 - (F_{Com}(t) - F_{Com}(0))} = \frac{(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t+1}{a}\right)^b}) - (1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{a}\right)^b})}{1 - ((1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{a}\right)^b}) - (1 - e^0))} = \frac{e^{-\left(\frac{t}{a}\right)^b} - e^{-\left(\frac{t+1}{a}\right)^b}}{e^{-\left(\frac{t}{a}\right)^b}} = 1 - e^{\frac{t^b - (t+1)^b}{a^b}}. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Appendix B

This appendix, using the 2-out-of-3 structure shown in Fig. 4(a) as an example, provides the 16 component state combinations required to solve for the optimal support strategy and presents the solutions for the optimal support strategy for each combination. Additionally, for these 16 state combinations, it details the quantity of functional components in the 2-out-of-3 structure that are in an available state under the optimal support strategy.

Table B.1 Optimal support strategy of the structure in Fig. 3(a)

Order	Component states $\{T_1, T_2, T_3, C_1, C_2, C_3\}$	Optimal support strategy	Number of optimal support strategy	Quantity of available functional components
1	{1,1,1,1,1,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_2 \rightarrow C_2, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_2 \rightarrow C_3, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_2 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$	3	3
2	{0,1,1,1,1,1}	$\{T_2 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$ $\{T_2 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_2 \rightarrow C_2, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_2 \rightarrow C_3, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$	4	2
3	{1,0,1,1,1,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$	3	2
4	{1,1,0,1,1,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_2 \rightarrow C_2\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_2 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_2 \rightarrow C_2\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_2 \rightarrow C_3\}$	4	2
5	{1,1,1,0,1,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_2 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_2 \rightarrow C_2, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_2 \rightarrow C_3, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$	4	2
6	{1,1,1,1,0,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_2 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_2 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$	3	2
7	{1,1,1,1,1,0}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_2 \rightarrow C_2\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_2 \rightarrow C_1\}$ $\{T_2 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$	4	2
8	{0,1,1,0,1,1}	$\{T_2 \rightarrow C_2, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$ $\{T_2 \rightarrow C_3, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$	2	2
9	{0,1,1,1,0,1}	$\{T_2 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$	1	2
10	{0,1,1,1,1,0}	$\{T_2 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$	1	2
11	{1,0,1,0,1,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$	1	2
12	{1,0,1,1,0,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_3\}$	1	2
13	{1,0,1,1,1,0}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_3 \rightarrow C_2\}$	1	2
14	{1,1,0,0,1,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_2 \rightarrow C_3\}$	1	2
15	{1,1,0,1,0,1}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_2 \rightarrow C_3\}$	1	2
16	{1,1,0,1,1,0}	$\{T_1 \rightarrow C_1, T_2 \rightarrow C_2\}$ $\{T_1 \rightarrow C_2, T_2 \rightarrow C_1\}$	2	2

Appendix C

This appendix provides the pseudocode for the optimal support strategy solving algorithm proposed in this article, namely the Hungarian algorithm with a DFS strategy. This tailored algorithm can specify the optimal support strategy of the system under any component state combination.

Table C.1 Tailored Hungarian algorithm with a DFS strategy

Algorithm: HungarianAlgorithmDFS
Input: Bipartite graph $G = \{\mathbf{T} \cup \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{E}\}$
Output: Maximum matching M and its cardinality cm
<pre> 1: $M = \{ \} ;$ 2: $\mathbf{vis} = \text{zeros}(2n,1);$ 3: $\mathbf{ma} = \text{zeros}(2n,1) - 1;$ 4: $cm = 0;$ 5: For each vertex T_i in $\mathbf{T}$ do 6: If $\mathbf{ma}(T_i) == -1$ do 7: $\mathbf{vis}(T_i) = 1;$ 8: If $\text{DFS}(T_i)$ do 9: Update M accordingly; 10: $cm = cm + 1;$ 11: End If 12: End If 13: End For 14: Function $\text{DFS}(T_i)$ 15: For each vertex C_j connected to T_i by edges in $\mathbf{E}$ do 16: If $\mathbf{vis}(C_j) == 0$ do 17: $\mathbf{vis}(C_j) = 1;$ 18: If $\mathbf{ma}(C_j) == -1$ or $\text{DFS}(\mathbf{ma}(C_j))$ do 19: $\mathbf{ma}(T_i) = C_j;$ 20: $\mathbf{ma}(C_j) = T_i;$ 21: Return true; 22: End If 23: End If 24: End For 25: Return false. </pre>

Appendix D

This appendix, as a supplementary material for the reliability assessment of the system in Section V. B, details the process for obtaining the analytical solution of the system reliability in the 30th year under scenarios 3 and 4.

For scenario 3, the system operates as a series-structured dual 2-out-of-3 system with a singular relation. Utilizing (1), the system's reliability is determined as following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(t) &= R_1(t) \times R_2(t) \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{T_1}(x) dx \right) \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{C_1}(x) dx \right) \right)^i \left(1 - \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{T_1}(x) dx \right) \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{C_1}(x) dx \right) \right)^{n-i} \times \\
 &\quad \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{T_4}(x) dx \right) \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{C_4}(x) dx \right) \right)^i \left(1 - \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{T_4}(x) dx \right) \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{C_4}(x) dx \right) \right)^{n-i} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_1}}} \right) \left(e^{-\lambda_{C_1} t} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - \left(e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_1}}} \right) \left(e^{-\lambda_{C_1} t} \right) \right)^{n-i} \times \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_4}}} \right) \left(e^{-\lambda_{C_4} t} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - \left(e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_4}}} \right) \left(e^{-\lambda_{C_4} t} \right) \right)^{n-i} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_1}} - \lambda_{C_1} t} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_1}} - \lambda_{C_1} t} \right)^{n-i} \times \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_4}} - \lambda_{C_4} t} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_4}} - \lambda_{C_4} t} \right)^{n-i}
 \end{aligned}$$

At the 30th year, the system reliability is calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(3) &= R_1(3) \times R_2(3) \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=2}^3 \binom{3}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{3}{14.96} - 0.11 \times 3} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{3}{14.96} - 0.11 \times 3} \right)^{3-i} \times \left(\sum_{i=2}^3 \binom{3}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{3}{13.76} - 0.14 \times 3} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{3}{13.76} - 0.14 \times 3} \right)^{3-i} \\
 &= 0.7280 \times 0.6858 \\
 &= 0.499
 \end{aligned}$$

For scenario 4, the system is configured as a series-structured dual 2-out-of-3 system with full relations. By applying (2), the system reliability is calculated as following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(t) &= R_1(t) \times R_2(t) \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{T_1}(x) dx \right)^i \left(\int_0^t f_{T_1}(x) dx \right)^{n-i} \right) \times \left(\sum_{j=k}^n \binom{n}{j} \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{C_1}(x) dx \right)^j \left(\int_0^t f_{C_1}(x) dx \right)^{n-j} \right) \times \\
 &\quad \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{T_4}(x) dx \right)^i \left(\int_0^t f_{T_4}(x) dx \right)^{n-i} \right) \times \left(\sum_{j=k}^n \binom{n}{j} \left(1 - \int_0^t f_{C_4}(x) dx \right)^j \left(\int_0^t f_{C_4}(x) dx \right)^{n-j} \right) \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_1}}} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_1}}} \right)^{n-i} \left(\sum_{j=k}^n \binom{n}{j} \left(e^{-\lambda_{C_1} t} \right)^j \left(1 - e^{-\lambda_{C_1} t} \right)^{n-j} \right) \times \\
 &\quad \left(\sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_4}}} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{a_{T_4}}} \right)^{n-i} \left(\sum_{j=k}^n \binom{n}{j} \left(e^{-\lambda_{C_4} t} \right)^j \left(1 - e^{-\lambda_{C_4} t} \right)^{n-j} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

At the 30th year, the system reliability is calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(3) &= R_1(3) \times R_2(3) \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=2}^3 \binom{3}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{3}{14.96} - 0.11 \times 3} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{3}{14.96} - 0.11 \times 3} \right)^{3-i} \left(\sum_{j=2}^3 \binom{3}{j} \left(e^{-0.11 \times 3} \right)^j \left(1 - e^{-0.11 \times 3} \right)^{3-j} \right) \times \\
 &\quad \left(\sum_{i=2}^3 \binom{3}{i} \left(e^{-\frac{3}{13.76} - 0.14 \times 3} \right) \right)^i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{3}{13.76} - 0.14 \times 3} \right)^{3-i} \left(\sum_{j=2}^3 \binom{3}{j} \left(e^{-0.14 \times 3} \right)^j \left(1 - e^{-0.14 \times 3} \right)^{3-j} \right) \\
 &= 0.9791 \times 0.8074 \times 0.9937 \times 0.7278 \\
 &= 0.572
 \end{aligned}$$